

Reactive iron carbonyl reagents for conversion of alkynes to cyclobutenediones, cyclic imides and anhydrides via double carbonylation[†]

Mallesh Beesu and Mariappan Periasamy*

School of Chemistry, University of Hyderabad, Central University P.O., Hyderabad-500 046, India

E-mail : mpssc@uohyd.ernet.in

Manuscript received 06 August 2013, accepted 07 August 2013

Abstract : Methods have been developed for the preparation of reactive iron carbonyl reagents for dicarbonylation of alkynes under various reaction conditions. In most cases, the cyclobutenediones were obtained in moderate to good yields (27–93%). In some cases, the iron carbonyl intermediates were converted to the corresponding benzoquinones (51–80%), cyclic imides (45–65%) and cyclic anhydrides (60–80%) in reasonable yields. The mechanistic pathways and intermediates involved in these processes are discussed.

Keywords : Iron carbonyl reagents, double carbonylation, alkynes, cyclobutenediones, benzoquinones, cyclic imides, anhydrides.

Introduction

The cyclobutenedione derivatives have been widely used in organic synthesis^{1–10} to prepare multifunctional organic molecules^{11,12}, molecules with NLO properties¹³, anion recognition systems^{14,15} and chiral ligands¹⁶. A large number of cyclobutenedione derivatives have also proven to exhibit interesting biological activities^{17–27}.

Cyclobutenediones are quinones of unstable cyclobutadienes because of their formal resemblance to cyclobutadienes by virtue of all sp^2 hybridised carbons in a four-membered ring^{28–30}. Also, the cyclobutenediones can be considered as resonance hybrids of a series of dipolar structures. Initial studies on cyclobutenediones were limited primarily to their unusual stability^{28–30}, vinylogous behaviour^{31–34} and aromaticity of their oxoanions (Fig. 1)^{35–38}. The dipolar characteristics of cyclobutenediones make the cyclobutenediones useful as reactive intermediates. Accordingly, there have been sustained efforts to develop new convenient methods for the preparation of these useful molecules.

Phenylcyclobutenedione, **1a** was the first cyclobutenedione synthesized by Roberts *et al.*²⁸ in 1955 from phenylacetylene and trifluorochloroethylene via 1,1,2-trifluoro-2-chloro-3-phenylcyclobutene **4** (Scheme 1).

Fig 1. Resonance structures of cyclobutenediones.

Generally, cyclobutenediones and its derivatives are synthesized via cycloaddition reaction of substituted acetylenes with tetrahaloethylene or dihaloketene (Scheme 2)³⁹.

Another widely used method involves the use of squaric acid derivatives (Scheme 3)³⁹.

We have undertaken efforts to prepare reactive iron carbonyl reagents from readily accessible iron carbonyls

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1. Phenyl cyclobutenedione from phenyl acetylene.

Scheme 2. Cyclobutenediones via cycloaddition of alkynes.

Scheme 3. Cyclobutenediones via squaric acid derivatives.

for developing new organic synthetic methods⁴⁰. In this review, we describe the results of investigations on the reaction of reactive iron carbonyl reagents with alkynes for cyclobutenediones synthesis.

Reaction of alkynes with iron complexes

In recent years, the metal carbonyls are increasingly used in organic synthesis. Many transition metals form stable neutral metal carbonyls, anionic metal carbonyls, hydrido metal carbonyls and their derivatives⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. These carbonyl complexes display unique reactivities in isomerization, oligomerization, carbonylation and polymerization processes⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. The metal carbonyls have been also used extensively in C-C bond forming reactions⁴⁹⁻⁵¹. Among various transition metal carbonyls, the organoiron complexes have been widely used in many of these processes⁵¹.

Organoiron chemistry was started by the discovery of pentacarbonyliron in 1891 independently by Mond⁵² and Berthelot⁵³. Another milestone was the discovery of the organometallic complex ferrocene in 1951 by Kealy and Pauson⁵⁴. Reppe first reported that, in the presence of NaOH, Fe(CO)₅ and acetylene **2b** react to give the iron complex of the formula (HC=CH)H₂Fe₂(CO)₈ **8**⁵⁵. The

structure of this iron complex containing two acidic hydrogens was proposed by Steinberg *et al.*⁵⁶ (Scheme 4). An improved method for the preparation of the complex **8** was also reported⁵⁶.

Scheme 4. Acetylene diron complex from acetylene/Fe(CO)₅/NaOH.

Later, Hock *et al.*⁵⁷ also studied the organoiron complexes reported by Reppe⁵⁵. They isolated the iron complex **9** in the reaction of but-2-yne **2c** with alkaline solution of Fe(CO)₅. The structure of the iron complex **9** was determined by X-ray crystallographic data (Scheme 5)⁵⁷.

In 1963, Whiting⁵⁸ reported that acetylene reacts with the reactive iron carbonyl species, generated from Fe(CO)₅/NaOH reagent system, to give a ferrole complex **10**. This complex produced the corresponding

Scheme 5. Alkynes to ferroles.

cyclobutenediones **1** in low yield (10%) upon $FeCl_3$ oxidation (Scheme 6)⁵⁸.

Scheme 6. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones via ferroles using $Fe(CO)_5/NaOH/FeCl_3$.

Synthesis of cyclobutenediones via reaction of $NaHFe(CO)_4$ reagent system with alkynes

Initially, we have investigated the reaction of the $NaHFe(CO)_4$ readily accessed from $Fe(CO)_5$ with alkynes (Scheme 7). We have observed that cyclobutenediones were obtained in reasonable yields using the $NaHFe(CO)_4/CH_3I$ reagent system⁵⁹. The iron carbonyl species, generated in this way, reacts with alkynes to give the corresponding cyclobutenediones **1** (27–42%) and the α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids **13** (10–22%), presumably via the maleoyl complex of type **11** and α,β -unsaturated acyl iron complex of the type **12** respectively after $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ oxidation (Scheme 7)⁵⁹.

Reaction of $FeCl_3/NaBH_4/CO$ reagent system with alkynes

The $NaHFe(CO)_4$ species could also be readily prepared using the $FeCl_3/NaBH_4/CO$ combination. The iron carbonyl reagent prepared in this way reacts with alkynes to give a complex **11** that yields the corresponding cyclobutenediones **1** after $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ oxidation at 25 °C (Scheme 9)⁶¹. Interestingly, it was observed that the reagent system converts alkynes to the corresponding benzoquinones **15** and **16** when the reaction was carried out at refluxing conditions, presumably via the intermediate complex **14**⁶¹.

Scheme 7. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones and α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids using $NaHFe(CO)_4/CH_3I/CuCl_2$.

Scheme 8. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones or α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids using $\text{NaHFe}(\text{CO})_4/\text{Me}_3\text{SiCl}/\text{CuCl}_2$.

Scheme 9. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones or benzoquinones using $\text{FeCl}_3/\text{NaBH}_4/\text{CO}/\text{CuCl}_2$.

Reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{NaBH}_4$ reagent system with alkynes

The $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{NaBH}_4$ reagent system reacts with alkynes in the presence of CH_3COOH to give the cyclobutenediones **1** in good yields (60–73%) after $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ oxidation (Scheme 10)⁶². Presumably, the reaction goes through the corresponding maleoyl complexes of type **11**. Interestingly, the cyclic imide **17** was obtained in 55–64% yield, when the reaction was carried out using large excess of primary amines (10 mol equiv.)⁶⁵.

Reaction of alkyne with the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{NaH}$ reagent system

The iron carbonyl complexes prepared *in situ* using the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{NaH}/\text{MeI}$ reagent combination and alkynes

2 at 25 °C give the corresponding cyclobutenediones **1** in 50–65% yields after $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ oxidation (Scheme 11)⁶³.

Reaction of alkyne with $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ /amine reagent system

Whereas coordinatively unsaturated iron carbonyl species, prepared using the $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ and *n*- BuNH_2 reagent combination, react with alkynes under ambient conditions to afford cyclobutenediones **1** (Scheme 12)⁶⁴, the use of excess of amine (10 equiv.) give the corresponding cyclic imides **17** (45–65%)⁶⁵.

The alkyne iron carbonyl complexes, prepared using the $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ and Et_3N in THF, react with Et_3N and acid chlorides to give the acyloxyferrole complexes of the type **18**, which afford the corresponding cyclobutene-

Scheme 10. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones or cyclic imides using $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{NaBH}_4/\text{R}''\text{NH}_2/\text{CuCl}_2$.

Scheme 11. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones using $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{NaH}/\text{CH}_3\text{I}/\text{CuCl}_2$.

Scheme 12. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones or cyclic imides using $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}/n\text{-BuNH}_2/\text{CuCl}_2$.

diones **1** in 60-90% yields upon reaction with bromine (Scheme 13)⁶⁶.

Reaction of alkyne with the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{Me}_3\text{NO}$ reagent system

The Me_3NO reagent has been reported to react with

$\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ to give the CO_2 and unsaturated iron carbonyls⁶⁷. We have found that the iron carbonyl complex prepared in this way reacts with alkynes at 25°C to give the corresponding cyclobutenediones **1** in moderate to good yields (50-75%) or the corresponding cyclic anhydrides

Scheme 13. Isolation of ferrole intermediate.

20 in good yields after $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ oxidation (Scheme 14)⁶⁸.

Since the 1,2-diacyloxyferrole complex **21** is formed in the present transformation using $t\text{-BuOK}/\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$, the

Scheme 14. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones and cyclic anhydrides using $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/\text{Me}_3\text{NO}/\text{CuCl}_2$.

Reaction of alkynes with the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/t\text{-BuOK}$ and $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9/t\text{-BuOK}$ reagent system

The $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ was reported to react with KOH to give $\text{KHF}(\text{CO})_4$ ⁴⁸. We have investigated the use of alkoxides to prepare the coordinatively unsaturated iron carbonyl species from $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$. We have observed that $t\text{-BuOK}$ reacts with $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ to give reactive iron carbonyl intermediates which in turn reacts with alkynes **2** at $70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to give the corresponding cyclobutenediones **1** in 70–93% yields after $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ oxidation (Scheme 15)⁶⁹.

It was observed that addition of Et_3N and acetyl chloride to the alkyne-iron carbonyl complex, formed in the reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ with $t\text{-BuOK}$ and alkyne **2d** in THF, leads to the formation of the 1,2-acyloxyferrole complex **21** in good yields 75% (Scheme 16). The structure of the acyloxyferrole complex **21** was identified by single crystal X-ray analysis⁶⁹.

Scheme 15. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones using $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5/t\text{-BuOK}/\text{CuCl}_2$.

reaction would go through a different type of double carbonylation of alkynes with sequential insertion of carbon monoxide at only one end of the acetylenic carbon in contrast to other methods discussed so far, in which the carbonylation takes place at both ends of the acetylenic carbons leading to intermediate of the type **18** (Scheme 13). Presumably, the reactions using the $t\text{-BuOK}/\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ reagent system (Schemes 15 and 16) would go by a different mechanism, as outlined in Scheme 17⁶⁹.

Scheme 16. Alkynes to 1,2-diphenyl ferrole.

Scheme 17. Mechanism and intermediates of the double carbonylation of alkynes.

Previously, it was reported that $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ reacts with metal alkoxides (*t*-BuOK or CH_3ONa) to give the corresponding $[(\text{CO})_4\text{Fe}(\text{COOR})]^-$ species **22** at 0 °C⁷⁰. We have envisaged that such species could decompose to give unsaturated iron carbonyl species as observed earlier using amine oxides and amines^{63–66,71,72}. Accordingly, in the present case, addition of ROM to the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ in THF would give the “ $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4$ ” species through such a decarbonylation (Scheme 17). These species could further undergo reaction with $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ to give species like $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_8$ via $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$. Such species could further react with alkynes, followed by CO insertion to give the ferracyclopentenedione of the type **26** or ferrole complex of the type **27** which could give the corresponding cyclobutenediones after $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ oxidation. The formation 1,2-diacloxyferrole complexes **21** here in contrast to 1,4-diacloxyferrole complexes **18** (Scheme 13) could be due to the presence of strong base, leading to

the nucleophilic intermediate **24** favoring another CO insertion in the adjacent carbon to give the intermediate species **25** (Scheme 17).

In the mechanism outlined in Scheme 17, the formation of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ is visualized. Accordingly, we have examined the reactivity of *t*-BuOK with $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$. Indeed, the $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ /*t*-BuOK reagent system also converts the alkynes to corresponding cyclobutenediones in 63–90% yields under similar reaction conditions (Scheme 18)⁶⁹.

Scheme 18. Alkynes to cyclobutenediones using $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ /*t*-BuOK/ CuCl_2 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, simple, convenient and easily scalable synthetic routes have been developed for the synthesis of cyclobutenediones, cyclic imides and anhydrides using readily accessible and inexpensive $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ and $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ complexes by using various promoters like Bu_3N , Me_3NO , NaBH_4 , NaH and $t\text{-BuOK}$. In these methods, the useful synthons cyclobutenediones, cyclic imides and anhydrides were obtained in single-pot synthetic operation using readily available reagents. Therefore, the methods described here involving preparation of reactive iron carbonyl reagents are useful for further synthetic exploitations.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge the DST support through a J. C. Bose National Fellowship grant to MP. This research work is also supported by the UGC under the "University of Potential for Excellence", the Center for Advanced Study (CAS) and the UGC-MHRD Chemistry Networking Resource Center programs.

References

- X. Shi, R. Amin and L. S. Liebeskind, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 1650.
- X. Shi and L. S. Liebeskind, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 1665.
- E. Pena-Cabrera and L. S. Liebeskind, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 1689.
- A. L. Aguilar-Aguilar, L. S. Liebeskind and E. Pena-Cabrera, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2007, **72**, 8539.
- K. H. Lee and H. W. Moore, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 735.
- M. Taing and H. W. Moore, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 329.
- L. A. Paquette, L. H. Kuo and J. Tae, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 2010.
- F. Geng, J. Liu and L. A. Paquette, *Org. Lett.*, 2002, **4**, 71.
- R. L. Danheiser and S. K. Gee, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, **49**, 1672.
- R. L. Danheiser, S. K. Gee and J. J. Perez, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 806.
- T. Kondo, A. Nakamura, T. Okada, N. Suzuki, K. Wada and T. Mitsudo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 6319.
- S. Zhang and L. S. Liebeskind, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1999, **64**, 4042.
- K. Y. Law and F. C. Bailey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1992, **57**, 3278.
- S. Tomas, R. Prohens, G. Deslongchamps, P. Ballester and A. Costa, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 1999, **38**, 2208.
- R. Prohens, G. Martorell, P. Ballester and A. Costa, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 1456.
- J. Zhang, H.-B. Zhou, S.-M. Lu, M.-M. Luo, R. G. Xie, M. C. K. Choi, Z.-Y. Zhou, S. C. Chan and T.-K. Yang, *Tetrahedron : Asymmetry*, 2001, **12**, 1907.
- L. F. Tietze, M. Arlt, M. Beller, K. H. Glusenkamp, E. Jahde and M. F. Rajewsky, *Chem. Ber.*, 1991, **124**, 1215.
- S. H. Gardner, P. Freyschmidt-paul, R. Hoffman, J. P. Sundberg, R. Happle, J. Nigel and D. J. Tobin, *Eur. J. Dermatol.*, 2000, **10**, 443.
- P. Freyschmidt-paul, J. P. Sundberg, R. Happle, K. J. McElwee, S. Metz, D. Boggess and R. J. Hoffman, *Investigative Dermatol.*, 1999, **113**, 61.
- M. Kazumasa, N. Motonobu, N. Miyako, K. Tatsuo and M. Yoshiki, *J. Dermatol.*, 2002, **29**, 661.
- N. B. Silverberg, J. K. Lim, A. S. Paller and A. J. Mancini, *J. Am. Acad. Dermatol.*, 2000, **42**, 803.
- K. T. Douglas and I. N. Nadvi, *FEBS Lett.*, 1979, **106**, 393.
- L. T. Burka, J. Doran and B. J. Wilson, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1982, **31**, 79.
- K. Sato, K. Seio and M. Sekine, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 12715.
- W. A. Kinney, M. Abou-Gharbia, D. T. Garrison, J. Schmidt, D. M. Kowal, D. R. Bramlett, T. L. Miller, R. P. Tasse, M. M. Zaleska and J. A. Moyer, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **41**, 236.
- M. Chan, R. J. Roon, J. F. Koerner, N. J. Taylor and J. F. Honek, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 4433.
- S. Tomas, M. C. Rotger, J. F. Gonzalez, P. M. Deya, P. Ballester and A. Costa, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, **36**, 2523.
- E. J. Smutny and J. D. Roberts, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3420.
- E. J. Smutny, M. C. Caserio and J. D. Roberts, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1793.
- M. P. Cava and M. J. Mitchel, "Cyclobutadiene and Related Compounds", Academic Press, New York, 1967.
- A. H. Schmidt and W. Ried, *Synthesis*, 1978, 1.
- H. Knorr and W. Ried, *Synthesis*, 1978, 649.
- A. H. Schmidt and W. Ried, *Synthesis*, 1978, 869.
- A. H. Schmidt, *Synthesis* 1980, 961.
- R. West and J. Niu, "Non-Benzenoid Aromatics", Academic Press, New York, 1969, Vol. 1, p. 132.
- R. West, H. Y. Niu, D. L. Powell and M. V. Evans, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 6204.
- R. West and D. L. Powell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 2577.
- M. Ito and R. West, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**,

- 2580.
39. A. Mukkanti and M. Periasamy, *ARKIVOC*, 2005, (xi), 48 and references therein.
 40. M. Periasamy, C. Rameshkumar, U. Radhakrishnan and A. Devasagayaraj, *Curr. Sci.*, 2000, **78**, 1307.
 41. I. Wender and P. Pino, "Organic Syntheses via Metal Carbonyls", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1977, Vol. 1 and 2.
 42. I. Haidue and J. J. Zukerman, "Basic Principles in Organometallic Chemistry", ed. Watter De Gruyter, New York, 1985.
 43. I. Beck, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1991, **30**, 168.
 44. J. E. Ellis, K. M. Chi, A. J. DiMaio, S. R. Frerichs, J. R. Stenzel, L. Rheingol and B. S. Haggerty, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1991, **30**, 194.
 45. L. S. Liebeskind, S. L. Baysdon, M. S. Souht, S. Iyer and J. P. Leeds, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 5839.
 46. J. P. Collman, L. S. Hegedus, J. R. Norton and R. G. Finke, (eds), "Principles and Applications of Organotransition Metal Chemistry", University Science Books, Mill Valley, California, 1987.
 47. K. Khumtaveeporn and H. Alper, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1995, **28**, 414.
 48. J. J. Brunet, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 1041.
 49. G. Wilkinson, F. G. A. Stone and E. W. Abel, (eds.), "Comprehensive Organometallic Chemistry", Pergamon Press, Oxford, New York, 1982, Vol. 1-8.
 50. E. A. K. V. Gustorf, F.-W. Grevels and I. Fischler, (eds.), "The Organic Chemistry of Iron", Academic Press, New York, Vol. 1, 1978 and Vol. 2, 1981.
 51. N. E. Schore, *Chem. Rev.*, 1988, **88**, 1081.
 52. L. Mond and F. Quincke, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, **59**, 604.
 53. M. Berthelot and C. R. Hebd, *Seances Acad. Sci.*, 1891, **112**, 1343.
 54. T. J. Kealy and P. L. Pauson, *Nature*, 1951, **168**, 1039.
 55. W. Reppe and H. Vetter, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1953, **582**, 133.
 56. H. W. Sternberg, R. A. Friedel, R. Markby and I. Wender, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3621.
 57. A. A. Hock and O. S. Mills, *Acta Cryst.*, 1961, **14**, 139.
 58. M. C. Whiting, *Chem. Weekblad*, 1963, **53**, 119.
 59. M. Periasamy, U. Radhakrishnan, J. J. Brunet, R. Chauvin and A. Elzaizi, *Chem. Commun.*, 1996, 1499.
 60. M. Periasamy, C. Rameshkumar, U. Radhakrishnan and J. J. Brunet, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 4930.
 61. C. Rameshkumar and M. Periasamy, *Organometallics*, 2000, **19**, 2400.
 62. M. Periasamy, C. Rameshkumar and U. Radhakrishnan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 7229.
 63. M. Periasamy, M. Beesu and D. Shyam Raj, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2008, **693**, 2843.
 64. C. Rameshkumar and M. Periasamy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, **41**, 2719.
 65. M. Periasamy, C. Rameshkumar and A. Mukkanti, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2002, **649**, 209.
 66. M. Periasamy, A. Mukkanti and D. Shyam Raj, *Organometallics*, 2004, **23**, 619.
 67. J. Elzinga and H. Hogeveen, *Chem. Commun.*, 1977, 705.
 68. M. Periasamy, A. Mukkanti and D. Shyam Raj, *Organometallics*, 2004, **23**, 6323.
 69. M. Beesu and M. Periasamy, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 543.
 70. P. Cabon, R. Rumin, J. Y. Salaun, S. Triki and H. D. Abbayes, *Organometallics*, 2005, **24**, 1709.
 71. T. Rajesh and M. Periasamy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, **39**, 117.
 72. T. Sugihara, M. Yamada, H. Ban, M. Yamaguchi and C. Kaneko, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1997, **36**, 2801.

